

THE USE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN PRACTICAL CLASSES ON THE NATURAL GEOGRAPHY OF CONTINENTS AND OCEANS IN 7TH GRADE

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Abstract. *Interactive methods are ways in which students are taught by a teacher based on the demand of the Times. In this article, a number of methods on the use of interactive techniques in the practical training of the natural geography of materials and Oceans of the 7th grade (such as strengthening their theoretical knowledge, forming the minds of students, solving problem situations) are given. As a result of the use of these methods, it serves to strengthen both theoretical and practical knowledge of schoolchildren.*

Keywords: *interactive methods, consolidation of theoretical knowledge, tasks for the formation of students' consciousness.*

Introduction

"Method – (Greek *metodos* – way of knowing or research, theory, doctrine) is a method of practical and theoretical acquisition, acquisition, study, knowledge of vocation, a set of instructions, methods, creation and justification of philosophical knowledge. The history of the origin of the method goes back to the practical activities of people. A person who has a method of doing something can do this job easier, faster and more quickly than others. And a person who does not master the method will take a lot of time and effort to do this. The method can be in practical or theoretical form in terms of its content. Methods of practical human activity also go back to understanding, knowing the laws inherent in reality. The doctrine of methods is called methodology in Science". [1]

The quality of the educational process at school depends on many factors, among which the methods and methods of teaching are of fundamental importance.

Traditional education uses one method or at most two methods of interactive technology. For example, the teacher speaks the topic to the student in each lesson. And the student listens as a listener. However, to this day it is seen that traditional education does not justify itself well.

Interactive method-serves to activate the acquisition of knowledge by students, to develop their personal qualities by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process. The use of interactive techniques will help increase the effectiveness of the lesson. The main criteria for interactive education are: the opportunity to conduct informal discussions, freely state and express educational material, the low number of lectures, but the large number of seminars, the creation of opportunities for students to take initiatives, the assignment of tasks to work as a small group, a large group, a class team, the performance of written works and other methods. [2]

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

In the implementation of the tasks of the present day, the requirements for the harmonious science of teaching with deep social religiosity are important in ideation.

In the practice of pedagogy, strange events sometimes occur. Students ask the teacher a question because of their curiosity, and at the same time the teacher cannot give a reasonable answer. When I answer incorrectly, I think that my next image will go away. For example, first graders ask the teacher what “space is” and he becomes confused. Indeed, how to explain this to first graders? Instead of studying carefully and answering the next day, the teacher immediately replied, “space is something very far from us.” After such an answer, some kind of idea of space is formed in readers? [3]

The classification of educational methods is as follows:

1. An ' traditional (according to source) methods of Education (E.I.Golant, N.M.Verzilin et al.
2. Educational methods according to the description of the cognitive activity of students (I.Ya.Lerner and M.N.Skatkin).
3. Educational methods according to the main didactic goals (M.A.Danilov and B.P.Esipov).
4. Binary methods of Education (M.I.Makhmutov).
5. Educational methods on a holistic approach (Yu.K.Babansky).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the practical training of the natural geography of materials and Oceans of the 7th grade, there are several methods on the use of interactive techniques (such as strengthening theoretical knowledge, forming the minds of students, solving problem situations). We will get acquainted with them below.

1. Tasks for strengthening theoretical knowledge.

Task " prove the hypothesis of mobilism from the map.”

- a) students are asked to write their thoughts on a given topic for 4 minutes.
- b) when the time runs out, the time is reported to be over. However, 1 minute is maintained. Because usually the best thoughts are born in a situation where a person is in a state of tension.
- c) The opinions of some of the students are heard. After the three-four students read their writing, the teacher asks the rest of the students who will have an idea that is not what they say.

2. Practical tasks for the formation of the consciousness of students.

Assignment. Interpret the terms given.

1. Mainland 4.Africa 7.Lake
2. Continent 5.Ocean 8.River
3. Eurasia 6.Sea 9.Australia

3. Tasks for solving problem situations.

Students marched 120 m from point A with 180 azimuths. It designated the location as Point B. From point B, they walked 120 m with 270 azimuths. He designated the location as Point D. They marched from point D with 360 azimuths. He designated the location as point E. The students are aynglarchi, how many degrees do they reach their place when they walk with Azimuth?

Conclusion

In place of the conclusion, it is appropriate to say that several methods for using interactive methods in the practical classes of the natural geography of 7th grade materials and Oceans, in particular, develop a number of positive characteristics, such as strengthening theoretical knowledge, forming students' minds, solving problem situations, keeping in mind in students, taking their position in different situations, As a result of the use of these methods, it serves to strengthen both theoretical and practical knowledge of schoolchildren.

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